

APPLICATION OF COMPREHENSIVE CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS FOR ADHESIVE INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. Adhesions can be defined as abnormal inflammatory attachments between tissue surfaces. The most common cause of abdominal adhesions is prior abdominal surgery, which begins to form within hours after the procedure and accounts for 60% of subsequent intestinal obstructions. Despite advancements in healthcare, significant challenges remain regarding prevention, diagnosis, and treatment, which have a substantial impact on morbidity and socioeconomic burden. Although various pharmacological agents and surgical strategies have been developed, none have demonstrated significant effectiveness in preventing adhesion formation [22].

Keywords: colorectal surgery, abdominal cavity, mesothelialization, peritoneum, omentum, colorectal surgery.

The aim of this review is to explore contemporary knowledge on the pathophysiology of adhesion formation, diagnostic and treatment options, as well as various methods of preventing adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO) in children [1,12].

The most important risk factors for adhesion formation in the abdominal cavity of children are the type of surgery and the extent of peritoneal damage. Surgeries in the lower abdomen and pelvis carry a higher risk of adhesion formation than those in the upper abdomen. The average time to the first ASBO-related surgery ranges from 0.9 to 1.4 years after colorectal surgery, 1.8 years after hepatobiliary surgery, 2 years after appendectomy, 4 years after stomach surgery, and 7 years after pediatric gynecological surgery. The incidence of ASBO is as follows: 23.9% after open adnexal surgery versus 0.0% after laparoscopic surgery; 0.2% after open cholecystectomy versus 0.0% after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. There is no statistical difference in ASBO incidence between laparoscopic and open appendectomy (1.4% versus 1.3%) [33].

The time of the first manifestation varies according to studies. Overall, 20% of cases occur within one-month post-surgery, 30% within one year, 25% within the subsequent one to five years, and the remaining 25% within five to twenty-five years. The relative risk of ASBO recurrence increases with subsequent abdominal surgeries, accounting for 1.6%, 1.8%, and 3.2% after one, two, and three or more abdominal surgeries, respectively [11,4].

ASBO is a common issue in general surgical practice, accounting for 20% of all emergency surgical conditions in children. Despite overall improvements in healthcare, it still presents significant challenges in terms of prevention, diagnosis, and treatment, exerting a substantial impact on morbidity and socioeconomic burden [10]. Adhesive small bowel obstruction is frequently confused with other etiologies of bowel obstruction, leading to dilemmas in choosing between conservative and surgical management. Although various pharmacological agents and surgical strategies have been developed to prevent adhesions, none have shown significant results

[25]. The lifetime risk of hospitalization due to adhesive small bowel obstruction in children after abdominal surgery is approximately four percent, with a need for laparotomy in about two percent of cases.

In the pathophysiology of adhesion formation, the visceral peritoneum plays a key role. It is lined with a single layer of mesothelial cells, loosely attached to the basement membrane, and easily detached even with minimal trauma. Peritoneal healing (mesothelialization) differs from skin healing, where re-epithelialization occurs from the periphery inward. In the peritoneum, surgical or traumatic defects are reperitonealized by implanting mesothelial cells into multiple areas of the defect [24]. When the peritoneum is damaged, detached mesothelial cells express cell adhesion molecules and various chemotactic factors, leading to a large influx of inflammatory cells, predominantly macrophages. Macrophages produce inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1, IL-6, and tumor necrosis factor (TNF), as well as anti-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-10 and interferon- γ (INF- γ). IL-6 is a potent adhesiogenic agent, while IL-1 and TNF are powerful inducers of IL-6. A higher ratio of inflammatory to anti-inflammatory cytokines promotes adhesion formation. These inflammatory reactions are directly proportional to the degree of peritoneal injury [20].

Adhesions are mainly classified as fibrinous or fibrous. Fibrinous adhesions occur in the early postoperative period; they are avascular, fragile, and typically fully resolve. Fibrous adhesions, on the other hand, are dense vascular adhesions in which the intestine attaches to the peritoneum, omentum, or other parts of the intestine. These tend to persist and cause intestinal obstruction [17].

ASBO can be classified as complete or partial, depending on the degree of obstruction, and as early (<30 days after surgery) or late, depending on the timing of onset. A study classified ASBO into Type I adhesions, which form in areas where no prior adhesions existed, and Type II adhesions, which represent reformed adhesions in areas where adhesions previously existed. Type I is further divided into Type IA, with prior operative procedures, and Type IB, where there were no prior operative procedures at the site of adhesion. Type II is also classified into Type IIA, where no surgical procedures other than adhesiolysis were performed, and Type IIB, where other surgical procedures were performed at the site of adhesion [10].

A child with ASBO, like with any other SBO, presents with complaints of abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, abdominal distension, and constipation. Abdominal pain is the initial and most prominent symptom, occurring in paroxysms at intervals of four to five minutes [30]. Gilroy Bevan's triad of adhesive pain consists of (1) pain that intensifies or eases with a change in position, (2) pain in the area of an old abdominal scar, and (3) tenderness elicited by pressure on the scar. Nausea and vomiting are more pronounced in high obstructions, while abdominal distension is more evident in distal obstructions. Constipation is a later development [16].

During clinical examination, the child may exhibit severe signs of dehydration. The abdomen may be distended, with scars from previous surgeries, if present. In the early stages of intestinal obstruction, peristaltic waves may be visible, especially in thin patients, accompanied by hyperactive bowel sounds that gradually diminish over time [3,26]. Mild abdominal tenderness may be present. Severe tenderness, guarding, and rigidity, along with fever, tachycardia, and leukocytosis, are observed in cases of strangulation and peritonitis. Hernias and intrarectal masses can be excluded through inguinal and rectal examinations, respectively [1,7].

Typically, plain abdominal X-rays are the first choice of examination due to their wide availability and low cost. They have a sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy ranging from 79% to 83%, 67% to 83%, and 64% to 82%, respectively, for diagnosing ASBO. The triad of dilated bowel loops (>3 cm in diameter), multiple air-fluid levels in an upright X-ray, and minimal air in the colon indicates SBO. The inability to differentiate adhesional obstruction from other etiologies and false-negative results in cases of closed-loop obstruction are the primary limitations of plain X-rays [14].

CT scans are not routinely performed due to their cost, limited availability, and the high radiation exposure to the pediatric body. They are typically used when the clinical history, physical examination, and X-ray findings are inconclusive. CT has a sensitivity of 90–94%, specificity of 96%, and accuracy of 95% for diagnosing ASBO in children [6,28]. A discrete transition zone with proximal bowel dilation and distal decompression, intraluminal contrast that does not pass beyond the transition zone, and minimal gas or fluid in the colon are indicative features of SBO on CT. Clustered bowel loops, the beak sign, the fat notch sign, and the feces sign are some specific features observed in adhesional small bowel obstruction [21].

Ultrasound (US) is one of the key methods for diagnosing adhesional intestinal obstruction, especially in children, due to its safety, high informativeness, and absence of ionizing radiation. The main advantages of US in adhesional obstruction are its lack of harmful effects on the body, which is particularly important for children, and its ability to quickly identify signs of intestinal obstruction without significant time costs [15,25]. US is highly informative, allowing visualization of pathological changes associated with obstruction, and is widely used for dynamic monitoring of patients to assess treatment efficacy [6,12].

Several authors have highlighted key ultrasound features of adhesional intestinal obstruction, such as dilated bowel loops: the proximal sections of the intestine are typically significantly dilated (loop diameter may exceed 3 cm); visualization of fluid levels within the intestinal loops, which is a characteristic sign; and altered peristalsis, which is notable in the early stages (e.g., peristalsis may be enhanced). As obstruction progresses, a decrease in peristalsis is noted, up to its complete absence in certain areas [31]. Detection of adhesions: adhesional bands may appear as hyperechoic linear structures connecting sections of bowel loops. Difficulties in visualizing adhesions may arise due to their thinness or deep location.

Additionally, Doppler studies can detect blood flow abnormalities, enabling assessment of blood supply in the mesentery and intestinal walls. Ischemia is indicated by reduced or absent blood flow, suggesting potential complications such as necrosis. Detection of free fluid may indicate inflammatory changes or a risk of intestinal wall perforation. Ultrasound (US) helps distinguish adhesional obstruction from other types of intestinal obstruction, such as intussusception, congenital malformations, or tumors. However, echographic features indicative of other pathologies (e.g., the “target sign” in intussusception) are absent in adhesional obstruction.

The method is actively used for monitoring the patient’s condition during conservative therapy (e.g., gastric decompression or correction of motility disorders) [27,7]. Ultrasound diagnostics play a crucial role in identifying and managing patients with suspected adhesional intestinal obstruction. It is a reliable method that allows rapid determination of the nature of the obstruction, identification of complications, and assessment of the need for surgical intervention [19,2].

A hyperosmolar water-soluble contrast agent is beneficial for patients undergoing initial non-surgical treatment. It has both diagnostic and therapeutic value. It draws water into the intestinal lumen, reduces bowel wall edema, and enhances smooth muscle contractions, potentially inducing effective peristalsis to overcome the obstruction. This test can be performed immediately upon admission or after initial traditional conservative treatment. It can rule out complete ASBO and predict the need for surgical intervention. Patients in whom the contrast does not reach the colon within 24 hours typically require surgery [31].

Small bowel enteroclysis is useful for diagnosing partial, intermittent low-grade small bowel obstruction. About 200–250 ml of barium followed by 1–2 liters of methylcellulose solution in water is introduced into the proximal jejunum through a long nasoenteric catheter, and movement is tracked fluoroscopically. It provides valuable information about the location, degree, severity, and possible cause of the obstruction. Limitations include the slow passage of contrast material in the fluid-filled hypotonic small intestine, the need for gastroenteral intubation, and the expertise required for the procedure [4,8].

In conclusion, all abdominal surgeries carry a risk of postoperative adhesion formation, which increases with subsequent surgeries. The severity of peritoneal damage and the imbalance between fibrin deposition and degradation during healing are the main factors triggering intra-abdominal adhesion formation. Plain abdominal radiography can accurately diagnose small bowel obstruction; however, CT and water-soluble contrast studies are more specific for ASBO. Ultrasound is a versatile tool that occupies a key position in modern diagnostics, especially in pediatric practice. Its use in adhesional intestinal obstruction in children allows not only for rapid diagnosis but also for monitoring treatment dynamics [13].

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